

Bulk hydroxylation and effective water splitting by highly reduced cerium oxide: The role of O vacancy coordination

Filip Dvořák^{1,a)}, Lucie Szabová²⁾, Viktor Johánek¹⁾, Matteo Farnesi Camellone³⁾, Vitalii Stetsovych^{1,b)}, Mykhailo Vorokhta¹⁾, Andrii Tovt¹⁾, Tomáš Skála¹⁾, Iva Matolínová¹⁾, Yoshitaka Tateyama²⁾, Josef Mysliveček^{1,*}, Stefano Fabris^{3,*}, Vladimír Matolín¹⁾

¹⁾ Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, V Holešovičkách 2, 18000 Prague 8, Czech Republic

²⁾ Center for Green Research on Energy and Environmental Materials (GREEN), National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), 1-1 Namiki, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-0044, Japan

³⁾ CNR-IOM DEMOCRITOS, Istituto Officina dei Materiali, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Via Bonomea 265, 34136 Trieste, Italy

*josef.myslivecek@mff.cuni.cz, *fabris@democritos.it

a) Present address: University of Pardubice, Faculty of Chemical Technology, Nám. Čs. Legií 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic

b) Present address: Institute of Physics, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Na Slovance 2, 18221 Prague 8, Czech Republic

Abstract:

Reactions of reduced cerium oxide CeO_x with water are fundamental processes omnipresent in ceria-based catalysis. Using thin epitaxial films of ordered CeO_x we investigate the influence of oxygen vacancy concentration and coordination on the oxidation of CeO_x by water. Upon changing the CeO_x stoichiometry from CeO_2 to Ce_2O_3 , we observe a transition from a slow surface reaction to a productive H_2 -evolving CeO_x oxidation with reaction yields exceeding the surface capacity and indicating the participation of bulk OH species. Both the experiments and the ab-initio calculations associate the effective oxidation of highly-reduced CeO_x by water to the network of next-nearest-neighbor oxygen vacancies present in the bixbyite c- Ce_2O_3 phase. Next-nearest-neighbor oxygen vacancies allow for the effective incorporation of water in the bulk via formation of OH^- groups. Bulk hydroxylation is proved to be absent in other CeO_x phases, where the average distance between oxygen vacancies is larger than in the c- Ce_2O_3 . Our study illustrates that the coordination of oxygen vacancies in CeO_x represents an important parameter to be considered in understanding and improving the reactivity of ceria-based catalysts.

Introduction:

In virtually every catalytic application, ceria-based catalysts are operated in water-rich environment. Of special interest is the interaction of water with reduced CeO_x relevant for reaction conditions in classical^{1,2} and emerging catalytic applications³⁻⁵ as well as for hydrogen production via thermochemical cycling of ceria.⁶⁻⁸ Thermogravimetry experiments reveal that, ultimately, reduced CeO_x is fully oxidized by water releasing H_2 as a product of water splitting. The process is kinetically limited by the rate of the related surface reactions.⁹ The effectiveness of oxidation of CeO_x by water has been studied by temperature programmed desorption (TPD) in model catalytic studies.¹⁰⁻¹³ These works suggest that the possibility of splitting H_2O molecules on CeO_x that leads to molecular H_2 and lattice O atoms increases with increasing concentration of O vacancies on the CeO_x surface. The small yields of this irreversible adsorption of H_2O are explained by static density functional theory (DFT) calculations that predict a high barrier to form molecular H_2 adsorbate from surface OH groups on stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ and reduced $\text{CeO}_x(111)$ surfaces¹⁴ as well as by ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations of the water/ceria interface.¹⁵

Compared to broadly studied surface chemical reactions on ceria^{16,17} interactions of reactants with ceria bulk constituted, until recently, a hypothetical option. In the case of interactions of H_2 or H_2O molecules with CeO_x samples hydrogen-sensitive experimental techniques are starting to provide evidence of subsurface and bulk hydride (CeH) and hydroxyl (OH) species in CeO_x .¹⁸⁻²⁰ Here, we identify a *bulk reaction channel* for the oxidation of CeO_x by water. We investigate, by means of surface science experiments and ab-initio calculations, the interaction of H_2O with thin films of CeO_x with well-defined geometry, stoichiometry, and crystallography. We observe an exceptional H_2 yield upon interaction of H_2O with bixbyite Ce_2O_3 , beyond the capacity of surface reaction. Ab-initio calculations reveal a key intermediate of this chemical reaction – bulk-stabilized OH groups resulting from H_2O dissociation. The stabilization effect is traced back to the geometry of OH incorporation in the network of next-nearest neighbor (NNN) oxygen vacancies present in the bixbyite Ce_2O_3 .

The role played by the spatial coordination of the oxygen vacancies towards the stabilization of OH in bulk ceria is further stressed by model calculations predicting a substantial stabilization of

OH on an isolated pair of NNN vacancies in CeO_x . This indicates the possibility of activation of the bulk reaction channel in real micro- and nanostructured ceria-based catalysts since a local increase of O vacancy concentration is being documented in near-surface regions,²¹ strained regions,²² and/or in the vicinity of dislocations.²³ The bulk reactivity of CeO_x represents a new *ansatz* in understanding and improving the effectiveness of ceria-based catalysis and energy conversion.

Results and Discussion:

Surface science experiments: Samples of bulk-reduced CeO_x are prepared by exposing epitaxial $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ thin films on a $\text{Cu}(111)$ substrate with metallic Ce as described previously.^{22,24} This procedure yields thin films that can be considered as terminations of ordered crystallographic phases of bulk $\iota\text{-Ce}_7\text{O}_{12}$, and bixbyite $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$,^{25,26} and of an ordered phase of intermediate stoichiometry, $\text{CeO}_{1.67}$.^{22,24,27} Schematic view of the film surfaces and of the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ reference are displayed in Figure 1, complete characteristics of the samples are listed in Table S1. This set of samples with graded O vacancy concentration and distinctly changing O vacancy coordination allows, in principle, investigating coordination chemistry of O vacancies in ceria.

We perform temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) of H_2O with a starting exposure on of 2.5 L H_2O at 100 K sample temperature. The results for mass 18 amu (key fragment ion of H_2O) are shown in Figure 1a and for mass 2 amu (key fragment ion of H_2) in Figure 1b. For the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface, the desorption of multilayer and monolayer molecular water is observed at approximately 150 K and 170 K, similarly to previous studies.^{10,12} The TPD spectra for the $\iota\text{-Ce}_7\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{CeO}_{1.67}$ samples display additional peaks between 500 and 600 K that correspond to the recombination of dissociated water molecules (Figure 1a), and to the recombination of surface hydroxyl groups producing H_2 (Figure 1b).¹⁰⁻¹² Finally, the TPD spectrum for the $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ sample shows no peak corresponding to the desorption of monolayer molecular water (approximately at 170 K in all other samples, see Figure 1a), while it is dominated by an intense desorption peak at approximately 500 K corresponding to the desorption of recombined H_2 molecules (Figure 1b). The latter peak indicates a very effective oxidation of $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ by water.

Figure 1: Results of TPD of H₂O on ordered thin films of c-Ce₂O₃, CeO_{1.67}, t-Ce₇O₁₂, and a reference CeO₂(111): (a) mass 18 amu, (b) mass 2 amu. H₂O exposure 2.5 L @ 100 K, and a schematic top view of these thin films. Black are the oxygen vacancies, white outlines represent the surface unit cells.

In all cases, the reaction of CeO_x samples with water is causing oxidation of the samples. Repeating the TPD of H₂O on the samples from Figure 1 thus generates samples with structure changing from c-Ce₂O₃ to CeO_{1.67} and t-Ce₇O₁₂ and allows investigating the reaction of H₂O with samples of an intermediate structure and stoichiometry. H₂ and H₂O yields from repeated TPD measurements including the yields from TPD in Figure 1 are presented in Figures 2a,b. The accompanying evolution of the CeO_x sample stoichiometry x as obtained from X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) of Ce 3d²⁸ is presented in Figure 2c. The sample with the initial geometry and stoichiometry of c-Ce₂O₃ displays effective oxidation and a considerable H₂ production during the first 4 cycles of H₂O adsorption and TPD. After the 4th H₂O adsorption and TPD cycle, the oxidation of the sample slows down to minute changes of the CeO_x stoichiometry of about Δx=0.005 per each TPD cycle. This slow-down of the reaction yield occurs when the sample stoichiometry approaches the stoichiometry of the CeO_{1.67} sample.

Figure 2: Repeated H₂O adsorption/TPD cycles on the samples from Figure 1. Cycle 0 – before TPD, cycle 1 – data from Figure 1, H₂O exposure 2.5 L @ 100 K, cycle > 1 – subsequent cycles, H₂O exposure 5 L @ 100 K. (a) H₂ recombination yield. (b) H₂O recombination yield. (c) Stoichiometry of the samples averaged over XPS information depth. (d) Area of the OH peak in O 1s SRPES spectrum of water-exposed samples measured @ 300 K. (e) LEED pattern of the samples at characteristic stages of the experiment measured at 64 eV; cf. panel (c). ① 4×4, ②, ③ transition from 4×4 to 3×3, ④ 3×3, ⑤ $\sqrt{7}\times\sqrt{7}$. Lines in (a-d) represent guides to the eyes.

The oxidation of the c-Ce₂O₃ sample involves the nucleation and growth of the CeO_{1.67} surface phase at the expense of the c-Ce₂O₃ phase, without participation of other surface phases. The coexistence of the c-Ce₂O₃ and CeO_{1.67} surface phases is observed by STM on partly oxidized c-Ce₂O₃ samples (Figure S1). It is also confirmed by the electron diffraction (LEED) reported in Figure 2e. The LEED patterns obtained during repeated H₂O adsorption/TPD experiments on the c-Ce₂O₃ sample (Figure 2e, ①-③) show the gradual conversion of the c-Ce₂O₃ (4×4 LEED pattern) into the CeO_{1.67} phase (3×3 LEED pattern).^{22,29} The effective oxidation and the considerable H₂ production upon interaction of CeO_x with water observed during repeated TPD on the c-Ce₂O₃ sample can thus be attributed solely to the c-Ce₂O₃ phase, while the CeO_{1.67} and t-Ce₇O₁₂ phases (Figure 2e, ④,⑤) exhibit slow oxidation kinetics.

The oxidation of CeO_x by water has been traditionally interpreted as a surface chemical reaction in which the surface OH groups recombine to form H₂ molecules and lattice O species.^{10,12,14} However, the high hydrogen yields measured upon interaction of c-Ce₂O₃ with H₂O indicate that H atoms can be accumulated as bulk species in c-Ce₂O₃ during water exposure and can be subsequently released at higher temperatures. Indeed, H₂ yield as high as 8×10¹⁴ cm⁻² is observed (Figure 2a, 1st TPD) corresponding to oxidation of 5-6 monolayers of c-Ce₂O₃ to CeO_{1.67} in one TPD cycle. A monolayer (ML) represents a stack of O, Ce and O layers as in CeO₂(111). In terms of O vacancy concentration the transition from c-Ce₂O₃ to CeO_{1.67} represents a change from 4×10¹⁴ cm⁻² to 2.6×10¹⁴ cm⁻² O vacancies in 1 ML. O vacancy concentration is calculated relative to O concentration in 1 ML of CeO₂.

Interestingly, H₂ yield upon repeated H₂O adsorption/TPD cycles of H₂O from c-Ce₂O₃ seems to be independent of the amount of OH on the sample surface. The amount of surface OH has been measured by highly surface-sensitive synchrotron radiation photoelectron spectroscopy (SRPES) at hv=640 eV. The area of the OH peak in SRPES O1s spectrum measured at 300 K during different H₂O adsorption-desorption cycles is plotted in Figure 2d. This SRPES OH signal is almost constant for samples that differ in H₂ yield by as much as 1 order of magnitude (cf. c-Ce₂O₃ and t-Ce₇O₁₂ samples upon 1st TPD). This observation indicates that, prior to desorption, OH groups on highly reduced samples must be partly incorporated in the bulk where their SRPES signal is attenuated (see Appendix 1 in the Supporting information).

Ab-initio calculations: We perform periodic DFT calculations aiming at identifying the origin of the high H₂ yield observed for the oxidation of the c-Ce₂O₃ phase by water. Since, apparently, the kinetics of the H₂ evolution is sufficiently fast to perform TPD experiments, we focus on explaining the thermodynamic origin of the observed phenomena. In order to support the hypothesis that water can be accumulated in the bulk of c-Ce₂O₃ and to understand the influence of these bulk OH species on the H₂ desorption measured in the TPD experiments, we calculate the reaction free energy for two relevant reactions: A) water incorporation into the bulk of different CeO_x systems during water exposure and B) hydrogen desorption during the TPD experiments. To this end, we perform two sets of calculations addressing the corresponding reactions:

We investigate CeO_x systems ($x=n/m$) differing in the number and arrangement of O vacancies, with $1.5 \leq x \leq 2$ (see Methods and Figure S2). In the reactions 1A and 1B, Ce_mO_{n-1}(OH)₂ and Ce_mO_{n+1} denote the systems resulting from incorporating one water molecule in the CeO_x bulk supercells and from the subsequent desorption of one hydrogen molecule, respectively. The ab-initio thermodynamics approach³⁰ is used to calculate the reaction Gibbs free energies

$$\Delta G_{\text{A}}(T, p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) = E[\text{Ce}_m\text{O}_{n-1}(\text{OH})_2] - E[\text{Ce}_m\text{O}_n] - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(T, p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) \quad [2\text{A}]$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{B}}(T, p_{\text{H}_2}) = E[\text{Ce}_m\text{O}_{n+1}] - E[\text{Ce}_m\text{O}_{n-1}(\text{OH})_2] + \mu_{\text{H}_2}(T, p_{\text{H}_2}), \quad [2\text{B}]$$

on the basis of the total energy E of the different systems calculated at $T = 0$ K and of the chemical potentials μ of the gas-phase molecular species involved in the reactions. The latter terms include the zero point energy (calculated) and entropic contributions (taken from experimental data in thermodynamic tables).³¹ Following previous works³² the entropic contributions to the free energy differences from the solid systems are neglected.

	Initial	Final	ΔG_A [eV/H ₂ O] T=0, P=0	ΔG_A [eV/H ₂ O] T=100K, P=3×10 ⁻⁶ Pa
CeO _{1.968}	Ce ₃₂ O ₆₃	Ce ₃₂ O ₆₂ (OH) ₂	-0.01 eV	0.21 eV
CeO _{1.875}	Ce ₈ O ₁₅	Ce ₈ O ₁₄ (OH) ₂	0.00 eV	0.22 eV
CeO _{1.75}	Ce ₈ O ₁₄	Ce ₈ O ₁₃ (OH) ₂	-0.01 eV	0.21 eV
c-Ce ₂ O ₃	Ce ₃₂ O ₄₈	Ce ₃₂ O ₄₇ (OH) ₂	-0.31 eV	-0.09 eV
c-Ce ₂ O ₃	Ce ₃₂ O ₄₈	32 Ce(OH) ₃	-1.23 eV	-1.01 eV
CeO _{1.937}	Ce ₃₂ O ₆₂	Ce ₃₂ O ₆₁ (OH) ₂	-0.22 eV	0.00 eV

Table 1: Stoichiometry of the supercells used to model water incorporation into bulk CeO_x systems and corresponding reaction energy per water molecule calculated on the basis of the total energies at T = 0 K and of the Gibbs free energies at the experimental conditions of water adsorption (T = 100 K and P_{H₂O} = 3×10⁻⁶ Pa). “Initial” and “Final” indicate the composition of the periodic supercells used to model the reactant and products, respectively.

The CeO_x systems considered in the calculations for the water incorporation reaction are reported in Table 1, where we describe the stoichiometry and the actual numbers of atoms present in the supercells modeling the initial and final states of the reactions. For all the reduced CeO_x systems investigated in this work, the incorporation of a water molecule at a bulk O vacancy yields its spontaneous dissociation and two bulk OH⁻ groups, one of them filling the existing O vacancy, the other resulting from proton binding to an O atom neighboring to the O vacancy. Similarly to the case of water dissociation at a surface O vacancy^{33,34} the process does not modify the number of reduced Ce³⁺ ions in CeO_x. Note that we have also considered the possible formation of H-species at O vacancies but these turn out not to be relevant for the water dissociation and accumulation in reduced bulk ceria. This issue will be discussed later in the context of ceria hydrogenation.

Figure 3: Calculated Gibbs free energy (ΔG_A) for water incorporation in a set of CeO_x bulk systems. The data are plotted for the partial pressure of H_2O measured during water exposure ($p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ Pa). Negative values of ΔG_A indicate favorable water incorporation in the bulk.

Water splitting: The reaction free energy ΔG_A for the water incorporation reaction calculated at $T = 0$ K and at the experimental conditions of water adsorption ($T = 100$ K and $P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ Pa, [2A]) are reported in Table 1 and in Figure 3. These DFT simulations show that the reaction ΔG_A for the bixbyite c- Ce_2O_3 phase is slightly negative and always lower than the ΔG_A for the partially reduced CeO_x systems. The calculations predict that water incorporation in bulk ceria is thermodynamically feasible only for the fully reduced c- Ce_2O_3 phase and for $T < 120$ K (see red line in Figure 3), while it is endothermic for the partially reduced $\text{CeO}_{1.75}$, $\text{CeO}_{1.875}$, and $\text{CeO}_{1.968}$ systems at all temperatures (black, blue and gray lines). Note that in our calculation, temperature favors water in the gas phase because of the large entropic contribution of the gas.

Figure 4: Top panels: Supercells used in the DFT calculations to model (a-c) CeO_x systems differing in the density and arrangement of O vacancies, and (d) cerium hydroxide. O vacancies (O_v) are displayed as purple spheres. Yellow and blue spheres represent Ce and O atoms, respectively. $d(\text{O}_v\text{-O}_v)$ denotes the minimum distance between vacancies. Bottom panels: Crystal environment around the OH groups resulting from water dissociation. OH(4) and OH(3) denote the coordination with respect to Ce ions.

Role of coordination of O vacancies: The simulations allow for identifying a structural explanation for the distinct properties of the $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ phase towards water bulk incorporation and dissociation, which we propose being controlled by the coordination and relative distance between O vacancies (O_v). In the partially reduced $\text{CeO}_{1.968}$, $\text{CeO}_{1.875}$, and $\text{CeO}_{1.75}$ systems, the shortest $\text{O}_v\text{-O}_v$ distance involves at least the fourth shell of neighboring O atoms in the O sublattice, i.e. 5.5 \AA , 7.8 \AA , and 11.1 \AA , respectively (see Figure 4a and Figure S2). Instead, in the $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ phase, the O vacancies are next nearest neighbors (NNN) in the O sublattice, and they form a network with $d(\text{O}_v\text{-O}_v) = 4.1 \text{ \AA}$ (purple spheres in Figure 4c).

The dissociation of a water molecule at an isolated O vacancy or at a pair of NNN O vacancies turns out to be very different, both from the structural and thermodynamic points of view. The 2 OH⁻ groups resulting from water dissociation at an isolated O vacancy in CeO_{1.968} are embedded in the pristine cubic fluorite structure of CeO₂ and therefore are both 4-fold coordinated by Ce ions (Figure 4a). The same is true for the more reduced CeO_{1.875} and CeO_{1.75} systems. As a result, when the O vacancies are well separated, $d(O_v-O_v) > 5 \text{ \AA}$, the free energy for water dissociation is weakly dependent on the density of O_v and H₂O: Ce₃₂O₆₃ and Ce₈O₁₅ yield the same reaction free energies (ΔG_A , Table 1 and Figure 3) despite differing by a factor of 2.3 in the density of O vacancies and of the incorporated OH species.

Instead, when a water molecule dissociates in the c-Ce₂O₃ phase, the network of NNN O vacancies allows for the 2 OH⁻ groups to depart from the 4-fold coordinated sites and to reach a more stable configuration in which one hydroxyl group is 3-fold and the other is 4-fold coordinated, respectively (Figure 4c). This is in perfect agreement with the general property of OH groups to be 3-fold coordinated in many metal hydroxides, e. g. Ni(OH)₂, Fe(OH)₂, Mn(OH)₂, Ga(OH)₃, Gd(OH)₃. Indeed, the largest ΔG_A is achieved by forming bulk cerium hydroxide Ce(OH)₃ (dark green line in Figure 3), in which all the OH groups are 3-fold coordinated (Figure 4d). The network of NNN O vacancies of the c-Ce₂O₃ phase thus facilitates the formation of the preferred 3-fold coordination of the OH⁻ groups.

We have verified this hypothesis by studying water dissociation at an isolated pair of NNN O vacancies in the cubic lattice of CeO₂. In this CeO_{1.937} configuration (Figure 4b), the distance between the O vacancies is 3.9 Å, thus very similar to the corresponding distance in the c-Ce₂O₃ phase, 4.1 Å (Figure 4c). Also in this case the more open structure due to the NNN O vacancy pair allows one of the OH groups for displacing from a 4-fold to a 3-fold coordinated site. Correspondingly, the calculated ΔG_A for this configuration (green line in Figure 3 and Table 1) is negative and almost as endothermic as the ΔG_A for the c-Ce₂O₃ phase, indicating a substantial stabilization of bulk OH⁻ on an isolated NNN O vacancy pair. NNN O vacancy pairs (or VV2 vacancies, in the notation of Ref. ²⁶) represent low energy vacancy configurations expected in bulk-reduced CeO_x.²⁶

Initial	Final	ΔG_B	ΔG_B
		T=0,P=0	T=550K,P=5×10 ⁻⁸ Pa
Ce ₃₂ O ₆₂ (OH) ₂	Ce ₃₂ O ₆₄	-0.20 eV	-1.56 eV
Ce ₈ O ₁₄ (OH) ₂	Ce ₈ O ₁₆	-0.725 eV	-2.08 eV
Ce ₈ O ₁₄ (H ₂ O)	Ce ₈ O ₁₅	-0.735 eV	-2.09 eV
Ce ₃₂ O ₄₈ (H ₂ O)	Ce ₃₂ O ₄₉	1.43 eV	0.07 eV

Table 2: Energy for H₂ desorption (eV/H₂ molecule) from the bulk CeO_x systems calculated on the basis of the total energies at T = 0 K and of the Gibbs free energies at the experimental conditions during TPD (T = 550 K and P_{H₂} = 5×10⁻⁸ Pa). “Initial” and “Final” indicate the composition of the periodic supercells used to model the reactant and products, respectively.

Figure 5: Calculated Gibbs free energy ΔG_B for H₂ desorption from bulk H species in CeO_x systems. The data are plotted for the partial pressure of H₂ measured during the TPD experiments (p_{H₂} = 5×10⁻⁸ Pa). Negative values of ΔG_B indicate preferential desorption of molecular H₂ in the gas phase from bulk H species.

On the basis of the thermodynamics and structural analysis presented above, we therefore conclude that the bixbyite $c\text{-CeO}_{1.5}$ phase is capable of accumulating water in its bulk at temperatures and pressures compatible with the present experimental settings. These results also show how water incorporation is mediated by the presence of NNN O vacancies in $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$, therefore pointing to the important role of O vacancy coordination in the chemical reactivity of CeO_x .³⁵

Hydrogen desorption: We now focus on the reaction 1B. The calculated reaction thermodynamics for H_2 desorption from hydroxylated CeO_x bulk systems is reported in Table 2 and Figure 5 at $T=0$ K (ΔG_B [2B]) and at the measured pressure during the TPD experiments (5×10^{-8} Pa H_2O , 5×10^{-8} Pa H_2). The singular properties of the $c\text{-CeO}_{1.5}$ phase stand out also in this case. OH^- groups in $\text{CeO}_{1.75} - \text{CeO}_{1.968}$ are thermodynamically unstable not only with respect to molecular water – as shown above – but also with respect to molecular H_2 . The calculated $\Delta G_B < 0$ for $\text{CeO}_{1.75} - \text{CeO}_{1.968}$ indicate preferential formation of H_2 rather than bulk OH^- groups. The stability of bulk OH^- groups in these phases is therefore ruled out. Instead, in the bulk of $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$, OH groups are predicted to be stable with respect to H_2 for a wide T range, up to ~ 570 K ($\Delta G_B > 0$). This is in good agreement with the experimental TPD data that identify a desorption peak of H_2 at $T \sim 520$ K from the $c\text{-CeO}_{1.5}$ sample (Figure 1b). Our calculations explain why this strong desorption peak is measured only on samples containing the $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ phase and unveil its atomistic origin. It results from dissociated water forming OH groups incorporated in the bulk of $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ during exposure at 100 K ($\Delta G_A < 0$, Figure 5). These bulk hydroxyls are stabilized by the favored 3-fold coordination which is in turn allowed by the network of NNN O vacancies of the $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ phase.

According to the calculations, H_2 desorption from the bulk OH^- groups in $c\text{-CeO}_{1.5}$ leads to $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ oxidation via partial filling of its O vacancies. We relate the reactivity of $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ and its water incorporation capacity to the intrinsic presence of NNN O vacancies and to their cooperative effect to stabilize 3-fold coordinated bulk OH species. Since the number of O_v decreases upon formation of bulk OH^- groups from water, the partial oxidation resulting from H_2 desorption should therefore decrease the water-incorporation capacity during repeated cycles of H_2O -adsorption/ H_2 -desorption. This is indeed compatible with the measured data during repeated TPD experiments (see Figure 2). We remark that both the bulk OH accumulation and the high

yield of H_2 production require sufficient hydroxyl bulk diffusion. Due to the supercell sizes, we could not address this kinetic issue. However, the experimental data suggest that bulk diffusion of OH is active in our thin-film c-Ce₂O₃ samples at low T and that it is not limiting the observed reactions 1A and 1B.

Hydroxylation vs. Hydrogenation of the CeO_x bulk: We point out an important difference in the reaction products resulting from water or hydrogen dissociation (i.e. hydrogenation) in the c-Ce₂O₃ phase that are schematically displayed in Figure 6. As reported above, water dissociation leads to bulk hydroxylation (Figure 6a) and to bulk incorporation of H in the form of OH⁻ species. According to this mechanism, partial oxidation of c-Ce₂O₃ is predicted only after H₂ desorption from the OH⁻ groups (Figure 6a, reaction [1B]), in agreement with the XPS measured parallel to the TPD experiment (Figure S3). For the case of c-Ce₂O₃ hydrogenation, our DFT calculations predict that the lowest-energy product involves the incorporation of H at bulk O_v sites in the form of H⁻ species, together with OH⁻ species (Figure 6b). This H⁻/OH⁻ pair results from the heterolytic H₂ dissociation. The H⁻/OH⁻ pair does not modify the degree of reduction of Ce₂O₃. This configuration is 0.73 eV lower in energy than the homolytic H₂ dissociation that forms two OH⁻ species (Figure 6c). Although these are the same products of water splitting, the OH⁻ pair resulting from the homolytic H₂ dissociation generates an excess of 2 electrons that cannot be properly accommodated by the fully reduced Ce³⁺ sublattice, increasing the energy of this product. We therefore predict that bulk c-Ce₂O₃ hydrogenation would entail heterolytic H₂ dissociation and H⁻ species, at variance of oxidized and partially reduced CeO_x ceria surfaces, where the homolytic H₂ dissociation is known to be preferred.³⁶⁻³⁸ We also note that reversing the reaction [1B] is not equivalent to the hydrogenation of c-Ce₂O₃, but to hydrogenation of partially oxidized Ce₂O₃.

Finally, the water and hydrogen dissociations in bulk c-Ce₂O₃ are different also from the thermodynamic point of view: the overall calculated free energy for water dissociation is slightly negative while for hydrogenation it is positive already at T=0 K (Figure 6b). Finite temperature will therefore make it even more endothermic because of the high entropic contribution of the H₂ reactant in the gas phase. It is however possible that the stability of H⁻ species at O vacancies is increased in partially reduced CeO_x, since these species are compatible with the hydride detected

by neutron spectroscopy in CeO_x ,¹⁹ and with bulk H species detected on CeO_x with nuclear reaction analysis.²⁰

Hydroxylation bulk c- Ce_2O_3

Hydrogenation bulk c- Ce_2O_3

Figure 6: Hydroxylation vs. hydrogenation of bulk c- Ce_2O_3 . Reaction free energy for the homolytic and heterolytic dissociation mechanisms calculated for $T=0 \text{ K}$. \square denotes an oxygen vacancy.

Having identified the origins of the c-Ce₂O₃ capacity to accumulate bulk OH groups at the experimental conditions, we can use the ab-initio thermodynamic approach to extrapolate the results at normal conditions of T and the partial pressures of H₂O and H₂. We plot in Figure S4 the dependency of the critical temperature T* on the partial pressure of molecular water (Figure S4a) and hydrogen (Figure S4b). We define T* as the temperature at which the reaction free energy turns from exothermic (T<T*) to endothermic (T>T*). This analysis shows that the bulk hydroxylation and effective water splitting of highly reduced CeO_x, as measured at UHV conditions, should be active at atmospheric pressure conditions, too (thin vertical black line). The effect of higher pressure is to increase the stability of the bulk OH species, which can be accumulated in the presence of water up to 200-300 K at p=10⁵ Pa. Moreover, atmospheric pressure would increase the onset for H₂ desorption from these bulk species to above 900 K.

Conclusions:

In the present work, we have identified a bulk reaction channel for oxidation of CeO_x by water. This reaction channel is activated during the interaction of H₂O with the bixbyite Ce₂O₃ phase. We have proven that the stabilization of the key intermediate of this reaction, the OH⁻ in the bulk of c-Ce₂O₃ is mediated by a particular spatial coordination of O vacancies – a network of next-nearest-neighbor O vacancies in bixbyite c-Ce₂O₃, and, more generally, by a pair of NNN O vacancies.

Our experiments and calculations clarify key aspects of the reaction pathways and reaction intermediates in the early experiments on H₂ generation by thermochemical cycling of CeO_x between Ce₂O₃ and CeO₂.⁶ In the present thermochemical and catalytic applications the CeO_x stoichiometry is usually far from Ce₂O₃.¹⁻⁷ Still, the NNN oxygen vacancy pairs mediating the productive CeO_x oxidation by water may appear and contribute to the reactivity of real micro- and nanostructured ceria-based catalysts. Due to the general correspondence between the vacancy formation energy and strain in ceria,²³ the accumulation of O vacancies and creation of active NNN vacancy pairs may be expected via introduction of dislocations, lattice distortions, heterointerfaces, and grain boundaries or cracks in the ceria samples.^{23,39-41} Our work suggests that controlling the concentration and the coordination of oxygen vacancies in ceria is a valuable

design principle that can foster the functionality of ceria-based heterogeneous catalysts, and that can be related to the more general concept of strain engineering of oxide catalytic materials.⁴²

Methods:

Surface science experiments: Experiments have been performed in the Surface Physics Laboratory (SPL) in Prague, Czech Republic on an experimental system combining Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM), laboratory X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), low-energy electron diffraction (LEED), and temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) techniques in-situ with sample preparation and cleaning. In parallel, experiments were performed at the Materials Science Beamline (MSB) at Synchrotron Elettra in Trieste, Italy where synchrotron radiation-excited photoelectron spectroscopy (SRPES) at $h\nu = 21..1000$ eV is available together with laboratory XPS, LEED, and sample preparation and cleaning.

Thin films of ordered CeO_x were prepared by the same experimental procedures in both facilities yielding the same sample characteristics as to the surface crystallographic structure (LEED), thickness and average sample stoichiometry (XPS, $h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) and the effectiveness of sample oxidation by water (evolution of XPS upon repeated TPD of H_2O , Figure 2c). The sample preparation has been described in detail in Refs.^{22,24} First, a continuous epitaxial thin film of $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ is deposited on a clean $\text{Cu}(111)$ substrate via thermal evaporation of Ce metal in O_2 background atmosphere. Substrate temperature is 523 K, O_2 pressure 5×10^{-5} Pa, growth rate 5 ML $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ per hour. After deposition, the thin film is annealed in the same O_2 background at 800 K for 10 min. The epitaxial thin film of $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ is further reduced by deposition of metallic Ce in vacuum at RT and subsequent annealing in vacuum to 900 K. This yields thin films of CeO_x with a distinct crystallographic structure due to the ordering of oxygen vacancies O_v (Figure 1). Care has been taken that samples of the ordered CeO_x exhibit single-phase LEED pattern indicating a homogeneous structure of the samples. In the case of superposition of two phases observed in LEED, the sample was further reduced by Ce and/or oxidized in a background atmosphere of 5×10^{-5} Pa O_2 to obtain a single-phase LEED.^{22,24}

In the SPL laboratory, TPD experiments were performed, and the sample crystallographic structure (LEED) and stoichiometry (XPS of Ce 3d) were investigated prior to and after the TPD cycles. SPL results are presented in Figures 1, 2a-c, S1, S3a, and S5a-c. In the MSB laboratory, the samples were exposed by water at low temperature and then annealed to increasingly higher

temperatures alternated with characterization of the surface crystallographic structure (LEED), sample chemical state (SRPES of O 1s, $h\nu = 640$ eV), and sample stoichiometry (XPS of Ce 3d, $h\nu = 1486.6$ eV). MSB results are presented in Figures 2d,e, S3b, and S5d. Methods of acquisition and quantification of the relevant experimental data are detailed in Figure S5.

Ab-initio calculations: The periodic spin-polarized DFT calculations have been performed using the PBE functional⁴³ and Vanderbilt's ultrasoft pseudopotentials,⁴⁴ as implemented in the plane-wave Quantum espresso code.⁴⁵ The basis set cutoffs for the representation of the electron wavefunction and density were 40 and 320 Ry, respectively. Integrals in the Brillouin zone were calculated on regular grids of $4\times 4\times 4$ k-points for the CeO_2 , $\text{CeO}_{1.968}$, and $c\text{-Ce}_2\text{O}_3$ phases, and of $6\times 6\times 6$ k-points for the $\text{CeO}_{1.875}$ and $\text{CeO}_{1.750}$ phases. A Hubbard U term⁴⁶ acting on the Ce-4f orbitals was added to the PBE energy functional in all calculations. In line with our previous works,^{38,47-49} the value of U equal to 4.5 eV was used. The pure and defective CeO_x systems with x ranging between 1.5 and 2 were modeled with the periodic supercells displayed in the Figure S2. These were simple cubic for the bulk CeO_2 (96 atoms), $\text{CeO}_{1.968}$ (95 atoms), $\text{CeO}_{1.937}$ and $\text{CeO}_{1.5}$ systems, fcc cubic for the $\text{CeO}_{1.875}$ and $\text{CeO}_{1.750}$ systems, and hexagonal for the $\text{Ce}_2(\text{OH})_3$ hydroxide. In all cases, the calculations were performed at the equilibrium lattice parameters of the corresponding systems. The free energies of the reactions have been calculated with the ab-initio thermodynamics approach.³⁰ See Supporting Information for additional details.

Supporting Information: Table S1, Figures S1-S5, Appendix 1 (pdf)

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TOC graphic:

